

NEW PHENOLIC TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The good performance of phenolic moulding compound with respect to fire makes it the only material capable of fulfilling the requirements that some applications need. Up to now however, the manufacturing of this type of materials required a corrosion-resistant moulding equipment, due to the use of acid catalyzed moulding compounds.

Iberia Ashland and Inasmet have developed a new range of Phenolic Moulding Compounds, whose non acid nature avoids special tooling during moulding. Their physical properties are comparable to Polyester Moulding Compounds, whereas flame and thermal performance are superior. On the other hand, the complexity of the formulation of this compounds have a great influence on the different manufacturing stages and the final properties of the finished products.

Keywords: BMC, flammability, Phenolic resin, Physical properties, SMC, Thermal properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Certain materials must face some behaviour requirements with respect to fire. The result is the development of new composite materials capable of meeting such requirements. It is within this context that Phenolic Technology became such an interesting topic (1). The Phenolic Moulding Compounds (SMC, BMC, TMC, ...) are materials with physical properties comparable to those of the Polyester Moulding Compounds. Moreover, their properties are better concerning fire and high temperatures (2). Table 1 shows the slight difference observed between both with respect to physical properties, while a big difference can be observed for the remaining properties; The HDT of the Phenolic SMC exceeds in the range of 100°C with respect to that of the Polyester SMC indicating therefore its high continuous use temperature and its excellent heat stability. At the same time, flammability is inferior in the Phenolic SMC (M1, IO >67) with very little smoke on burning (Dm = 42), and little toxicity (IF = F1).

An advancement of the study carried out by IBERIA ASHLAND and INASMET about the development of a new range of Phenolic Moulding Compounds is here reported. The main advantage of these compounds is their non acid characteristic due to the absence of a catalyst, as observed in Table 2. This was possible after developing a resin capable of curing without using a catalyst.

Property	Phenolic SMC	Fire-Retardant Polyester SMC
Tensile Strength (MPa)	82	89
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	10	12
Flexural Strength (MPa)	165	173
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	9.7	10.3
Izod Impact (J/m)	606	533
Interlam. Shear Strength (MPa)	19	20
HDT /1.82 MPa (°C)	300	200
Epiradiator Classification	M1	M1-M3
Oxigen Index	67	40
Specific Optical Density (Dm)	25	250
Smoke Index (IF)	F1	F3

Table 1: Comparison of Properties in Phenolic and Fire-Retardant Polyester SMC.

This paper is focused mainly on the great influence of the components of this moulding compounds on the different manufacturing stages (Fig.1) and the final properties of the finished product (3). Three different cases were considered.

- Influence of the different thickening agents on the compound maturation.
- Influence of different fillers on the mechanical properties of the molded parts.
- Influence of the release agent and flame retardant systems on flame behaviour.

2. FORMULATION

The formulation used is shown in Table 2. The exact quantity and quality of each ingredient depends on the type of compounding (sheet, bulk or thick moulding compound) and the requirements of the manufactured composite.

order to obtain synergism between the fibre and matrix properties, which is the characteristic of the composite materials.

Coupling is done by chemical bonding. The most difficult aspect is to find the right agent and to know the required quantities.

3. CASE 1. INFUENCE OF DIFFERENT THICKENERS OVER MATURATION OF THE COMPOUND.

Three different samples were prepared for undertaking this study case. They had all the components of a moulding compound except the fibre. The difference between them was the thickening system used. Mixture A had an alkaline-earth oxyde, Mixture B had another one of the borate family and mixture C had 50% of both components. The total percentage was the same in the three cases.

Once the mixtures were prepared, the viscosity variation with respect to time was studied by using a Brookfield viscometer at a shear rate of 4.2 sg^{-1} . Results obtained can be observed in Fig.2 where the difference in the three cases is quite obvious. Mixture A obtained the highest viscosity level. However, even if after 15 days a tendency to become stable is observed this did not definitively happened until 30 days.

The mixture B obtained the lowest viscosity and became stable after 13 days.

Mixture C displayed intermediate viscosity values with respect to above mentioned cases. After 30 days no tendency to stabilization was observed.

If viscosity becomes too high during the maturation period then an excessively fast ageing of the compound will take place before trasformation. This will result in a loss of both operative properties and flow capacity during transformation.

Fig.2. Kinetic of thickening with different thickener systems.

moldable material. This is a very important product for elaborating the Phenolic SMC. The paste (resin, fillers and additives) must show a low viscosity when elaborating the SMC as fibres must be impregnated avoiding impregnation problems. However, the viscosity of the compound must be high enough and stable with respect to time in order to assure a long storage time and to facilitate the removal of the carrier film and a uniform flow under moulding conditions.

Case 2 clearly shows the effect of the different thickening agents over viscosity during maturation.

Ingredients	Parts in weight
Resin	33
Fillers	31 - 35
Thickening agent	2 - 4
Release agent	0.5
Flame retardant	0 - 4
Coupling agent	0.5
Glass Fibre	27

Table 2: Phenolic Moulding Compound formulation.

2.5. Release agent

These additives are selected according to their melting point. It must not exceed the temperature reached by the compound during the moulding process. This is when the release agent in liquid state moves to the surface of the compound reducing adhesion at the interface with the mold surface.

It has been observed that thermoplastic release agents improve the surface quality of the SMC apart from detaching the surface from the mold, although the fire properties get worse in this case(Case 3).

2.6. Flame retardant

These additives improve the behaviour of the compound materials with respect to fire.

The phenolic resins are self-extinguishable but the M1 classification is not sometimes easily achieved due to the high quantity of components in each compound. Therefore, the use of fire-retardants is in some cases necessary, as observed in Case 3.

2.7. Coupling agent

The main objective of the coupling agent is to improve the wetting of the fibre with resin in

Fig.1. Variation of the viscosity of the compound along the manufacturing process.

2.1. Resin

The phenolic resin used is of the resol type from ASHLAND, Ref.R101. This resin has a low water content and low viscosity. The main advantage of such resin is its capacity of curing without using a catalyst which in most SMC cases are acids, eliminating therefore the special tooling requirements.

2.2. Fibre

The fibres, that ensure the mechanical properties of the final composite, are usually glass fibre and can be used as mat, discontinuous or continuous roving or cloth. The different shapes and distributions result in several moulding compounds and have a strong influence on the flow facility when moulding. INASMET is mainly working with short fibres with length not exceeding 25 mm and continuous mat, kindly supplied by VETROTEX ESPAÑA, S.A.

2.3. Filler

Many are the interests for adding filler to formulations: price reduction, modification of both rheological properties and reactivity, fire resistance increase, modification of the mechanical properties and surface aspect. It has been observed that this component has a strong effect on the different manufacturing phases. Therefore, the nature and percentage of this component will influence the viscosity when elaborating the compound, the maturation kinetics and flow during moulding. Case 1 shows the effect of different filler system over the mechanical properties of the final parts.

2.4. Thickening agent

Thickeners initiate the reaction that transforms the compound in a reproduceable and

4. CASE 2. INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT FILLERS OVER MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

This study was carried out starting from two BMC with different filler systems. While the BMC1 contained a unique calcium carbonate filler, the BMC2 had 50% of calcium carbonate and a second filler belonging to the silicate family. A 6mm long glass fibre was used in both cases.

After an adequate maturation period, these BMC were transformed in equal moulding conditions and subsequently were submitted to flexion, compression and interlaminar shearing tests. Result obtained are given in Table 3. All tests show a deterioration of properties when using the filler system included in BMC2.

Property	Units	ASTM Test	BMC 1	BMC 2
Flexural Strength	MPa	D - 790	89.4	55.5
Flexural Modulus	GPa	D - 790	9.1	6
Compressive Strength	MPa	D - 695	85.4	44.5
Interlam. Shear Strength	MPa	D - 2344	11.9	6.7

Table 3: Comparison of Physical Properties in two BMC with different filler system.

5. CASE 3. INFLUENCE OF THE RELEASE AGENT AND FLAME RETARDANT SYSTEM ON FIRE BEHAVIOUR.

The test chosen to make the comparison was the measuring of the oxygen index. This index indicates the minimum oxygen concentration, expressed as volume percent, in a mixture of oxygen and nitrogen that will just support flaming combustion of a material initially at room temperature under specific conditions.

The study was made with three different SMC formulations:

- A: 3% of release agent and a conventional filler without flame retardant character.
- B: 0.5 % of release agent and a fire retardant filler.
- C: 0.5% of release agent, a fire retardant filler and 4% of a flame retardant additive.

The rest of components in the compounds were the same in % and type in all the cases, as well as the maturation and moulding parameters. Afterwards, their oxygen index was measured. Results obtained are shown in Table 4.

Reference	Release Agent (%)	Filler System	Flame Retardant (%)	IO (%)
SMC A	3	Conventional	None	44
SMC B	0.5	Fire Retardant	None	60
SMC C	0.5	Fire Retardant	4	>95

Table 4: Oxygen Index Data for different Phenolic SMC formulations.

The decrease of the release agent percent together with the use of a flame retardant filler and additive, increase remarkably the IO, improving therefore the fire behaviour of the composite.

6. CONCLUSIONS

IBERIA ASHLAND and INASMET are developing a new range of Phenolic Moulding Compounds which will give the opportunity of being at the fire security level required nowadays. Such materials can be compared to the Polyester Moulding Compounds concerning physical properties and have better fire and thermal properties.

The main advantage of compounds here studied is that they show non acid character as no catalyst is added for curing. On the other hand, and due to the complexity of their formulation certain components have a strong influence over the manufacturing processes and final properties:

- The thickening system affects the maturation phase of the compound. The system to be chosen should be that one where a viscosity stabilization with respect to time can be obtained. At the same time, such viscosity must allow a proper operativeness of the compound before and during moulding. Mixture B is the adequate system in our Case 1 study.

- The filler system affects the final mechanical properties of the product. Case 2 shows that BMC1 is the compound with the best filler system.

- Due to the high additive content of the compound sometimes it is necessary to add some flame retardant agent to obtain a good fire behaviour, as it is demonstrated in SMC C of Case 3.

On the other hand, IBERIA ASHLAND and INASMET with the collaboration of SAPYS, from the VALENTINE group, are developing a painting system for the above mentioned materials. Results are expected to be available in the near future.

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